

Future Treatments for Epilepsy

Hello!

We are a group of doctors and researchers in London and are keen to understand your perspectives as a person with epilepsy or a carer for a person with epilepsy on current and future treatments. This is to help us design studies to improve future treatments for epilepsy, specifically those that involve electrical stimulation to reduce seizures, which is known as 'neuromodulation'.

This survey will be in 4 sections and should take about 20 minutes to complete.

- **Section 1:** This section is a short video will explain current and future treatments for epilepsy to help inform your answers.
- **Section 2:** This section will ask some questions about you and, if you are a carer, about the person with epilepsy that you care for.
- **Section 3:** This section will ask you some questions about current and future stimulation treatments for epilepsy.
- **Section 4:** This section will ask you some questions about our proposed DoVE trial.

Please note that we will not be collecting any identifiable information about you. We have given an option at the end to provide your e-mail address if you would like to be updated on the results of the survey and will use your e-mail for this purpose only. All data will be stored in compliance with GDPR.

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* Indicates required question

Section 1: Current and future treatments for epilepsy

Please take a few minutes to watch this video before moving on to the next section.

[http://youtube.com/watch?](http://youtube.com/watch?v=jVzndd1KJg8)

[v=jVzndd1KJg8](http://youtube.com/watch?v=jVzndd1KJg8)

Section 2: Some questions about you

1. Which one of these best describes you? *

Mark only one oval.

- A person with epilepsy
- A carer for someone with epilepsy

The following questions relate to the person with epilepsy (either yourself or the person you care for).

2. What age is the person with epilepsy? *

Mark only one oval.

- 0-19
- 20-39
- 40-59
- 60+

3. Does the person with epilepsy have a learning disability? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

4. Which region of the UK does the person with epilepsy live? *

Mark only one oval.

Greater London

South East

South West

West Midlands

North West

North East

Yorkshire and the Humber

East Midlands

East of England

Scotland

Wales

Northern Ireland

5. Has the person with epilepsy had any form of surgery for epilepsy? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

6. Does the person with epilepsy have a vagus nerve stimulator (VNS)? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Section 3: Current and future stimulation treatments for epilepsy

7. On a scale of 1-5, how likely are you to consider vagus nerve stimulation (VNS) for treatment of epilepsy? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very likely

8. On a scale of 1-5, how likely are you to consider deep brain stimulation (DBS) for treatment of epilepsy? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very likely

9. If neuromodulation (DBS or VNS) was deemed a treatment option for your/your * caree's epilepsy, how important are the following in terms of the goals of treatment?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Very unimportant	Unimportant	Neither important nor unimportant	Important	Very important
Reduce seizures (either frequency or severity)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Stopping seizures completely (seizure freedom)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Improving quality of life	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Improving mood	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Improving sleep	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Improving concentration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reducing the risk of sudden unexpected death in epilepsy (SUDEP)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

10. Which of the following put you off considering neuromodulation (DBS or VNS) for treatment of epilepsy?

(You may select more than one response)

Check all that apply.

- Side effects
- Requirement for follow-up
- Requirement for battery changes
- Thought of the procedure
- Other: _____

11. The risks of DBS and VNS are slightly different as one is an operation on the brain and the other is an operation in the neck. How important would you consider the following risks? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Very Unimportant	Unimportant	Neither important nor unimportant	Important	Very Important
A 1 in 100 chance of stroke	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A 1 in 100 chance of changing or affecting voice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A 1 in 100 chance of requiring a repeat operation to fix faulty equipment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A 1 in 100 chance of infection requiring removal of the device	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

- 12. VNS requires battery changes every 2-4 years, which is usually performed as a day case operation under general anaesthesia. DBS offers the option of being able to wirelessly recharge the battery, which can last up to 30 years. On a scale of 1-5, how important is this difference? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Very important

Section 4: Views on the DoVE Trial

As mentioned in the video, the DoVE Trial is a study we are proposing to test which of two stimulation treatments - deep brain stimulation (DBS) or vagus nerve stimulation (VNS) - may be better for people with epilepsy.

Usually, when someone does not respond to medication, they undergo tests which determine whether they may be candidates for surgery to help with their epilepsy. Some are offered VNS.

Our current plans are that, if someone is offered VNS, and wishes to participate in DoVE, they will enter the study and randomly assigned to one of the 2 treatments, either DBS or VNS. Following the operation, they will be followed up by the doctors and the research team for 2 years and, at the end of the 2 years, we will see how well each patient is doing. We will monitor their seizures, quality of life and other outcomes whilst also closely assessing how safe and what complications are associated with DBS and VNS respectively.

13. If you or your loved one had been referred for epilepsy surgery, would you be willing to enter our proposed DoVE trial and be randomly assigned to receive either deep brain stimulation (DBS) or vagus nerve stimulation (VNS) as a treatment for epilepsy? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

14. Please explain why you would or would not participate.

15. If there was the option, would you prefer to be offered both treatments (DBS or VNS) and choose which to proceed with? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

16. If the person with epilepsy has a learning disability, would it be ethical to get permission to participate in the study from their carer or next-of-kin? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

17. Please explain why you do or do not think this is acceptable.

18. Which of the following would be your concerns over such a trial? *

(You may select more than one response)

Check all that apply.

- Risks of the treatments
- Not knowing which is more effective
- Additional assessments and appointments associated with a trial
- Missing out on the treatment you wanted more
- Other: _____

19. In a trial, we usually assess people at multiple time points to see how they are doing. However, this comes at a travel and convenience cost. How frequent do you think visits should be? *

Mark only one oval.

- Once a month
- Once every 3 months
- Once every 6 months
- Once a year

20. If you were offered a trial, what factors would encourage you to take part?

(You may select more than one response)

Check all that apply.

- Potential to receive new treatments
- Closer care with increased appointments
- Chance to find out which treatment is best
- Ability to contribute to better care of people with epilepsy
- Other: _____

21. If you were in a trial, what factors would encourage you to stay in it (as opposed to leaving it)?

(You may select more than one response)

Check all that apply.

- Close follow-up
- Relaxed (infrequent) follow-up
- Compensation for travel and visits
- Other: _____

22. Do you have any further comments or questions about VNS, DBS or the DoVE trial?

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